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RESPONSE OF PADDY SEEDLINGS (*Oryza sativa* L.) TO VARIED GROWTH MEDIA COMPOSITION INOCULATED WITH *Piriformospora indica***Adarsh S.^{1*}, Ameena M.², Shalini Pillai P.³, Joy M.⁴, Jacob John⁵, Beena R.⁶, Naveen Leno⁷**¹Research Scholar, Department of Agronomy²Professor (Agronomy), Department of Agronomy³Professor (Agronomy) and Head, Department of Agronomy⁴Professor (Plant Pathology) and Head, CRS, Balaramapuram⁵Director of Extension, Professor (Agronomy) and Head, IFSRS, Karamana⁶Assistant Professor (Plant Physiology), Department of Plant Physiology⁷Assistant Professor (SS & AC), Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry^{1,2,3,6,7}College of Agriculture, Vellayani & ^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7}Kerala Agricultural University*Correspondence: ssadarshsss@gmail.com

The challenges in paddy cultivation include poor nutrient use efficiency due to lack of availability and uptake. *Piriformospora indica* is an endophytic root-colonising fungus that grows on various substrates and promotes plant nutrient uptake by increasing its availability in soil solution and its uptake through root hairs. A study to understand the potential of this endophyte is yet to be done in rice to tackle the challenges of enhancing nutrient use efficiency. A lab study was conducted at the Department of Agronomy, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Kerala Agricultural University to study the response of paddy seedlings under varied growth media composition inoculated with the endophyte. The components for growth media included; paddy soil, farmyard manure (FYM), vermicompost, neem cake, and coir pith compost mixed in different proportions. The paddy (var. Uma) seeds were sown once the endophyte multiplied enough in the media for colonising the seedlings. The experiment was completely randomised with eight treatments and nine replications. All treatments were maintained in the same growth conditions and were given the same cultural practices. The growth response was superior in seedlings grown in *P. indica* media prepared with paddy soil, FYM, and coir pith compost in equal proportion. The parameters such as germination percentage (92.27 %), seedling height (20.50 cm), number of leaves per plant (2.10), leaf length (15.30 cm), leaf width (3.27 cm), shoot dry weight (0.01 g per plant), and dry matter production (0.02 g per plant) were the highest and statistically significant in T₅. The study concluded that the endophyte, when cultured in growth media containing paddy soil, FYM, and coir pith compost, significantly enhanced the growth of rice seedlings with superior growth parameters when compared to the control, indicating the positive impact of the specific growth medium.

Keywords: Paddy, nutrient use efficiency, endophyte, *Piriformospora indica*